

Urea and ammonium sulfate topdressed in three equal splits did not differ significantly (see table). Band application slightly increased grain yield and N uptake over topdressing. Additional benefit with band placement was probably due to the low rate of nitrification.

Application of ATC, a water-soluble chemical recommended for nitrification inhibition, did not influence yield and N uptake of rice, even at higher rates. This may be due to ineffective coating and leaching of the chemical from the bands. Potassium nitrate was the most

Influence of N source and a nitrification inhibitor (ATC) on yield and N uptake of wetland rice. Ludhiana (Punjab), India, 1986 kharif.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)
	Grain	Straw		
Ammonium sulfate (topdressed)	7.6	8.8	124.5	11.8
Urea (topdressed)	7.2	8.8	113.2	61.5
Potassium nitrate (topdressed)	4.8	6.3	80.6	37.9
Urea (banded)	7.8	9.2	122.6	76.1
Urea + ATC (banded)	7.7	9.3	119.8	13.5
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.6	0.8	5.4	—
Control (no N)	2.5	3.5	38.9	—

inefficient N source. Recovery of N from potassium nitrate was about half that from ammonium sulfate and urea. □

Effect of plant density and fertilization on rice yield and fertilizer efficiency

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We studied fertilizer efficiency at different N P levels and different plant densities, with IR6 as the test variety.

Plant density and NP level significantly affected yield (see table). The highest yield was at 20- × 20-cm spacing (250,000 hills/ha) and the lowest at 40- × 25-cm spacing (100,000 hills/ha). The highest yield was with

Effect of plant density and fertilizer level on rice yield and fertilizer efficiency. Muridke, Pakistan.

Spacing (cm)	Plant density (hills/ha)	Yield (t/ha) at indicated NP (kg/ha) level				Mean for plant density ^a (t/ha)	N efficiency (kg rice/kg N) at indicated NP (kg/ha) level			Mean for plant density (kg rice/kg N)
		0-60	60-60	90-60	120-60		60-60	90-60	120-60	
40 × 25	100,000	3.2	5.7	5.9	6.3	5.2 c	42	30	26	33
25 × 25	160,000	3.2	6.0	6.1	6.7	5.5 b	44	32	28	35
20 × 25	200,000	3.5	6.2	6.4	6.9	5.7 ab	45	33	29	36
20 × 20	250,000	3.7	6.4	6.7	7.2	6.0 a	46	34	29	36
Mean for fertilizer ^a		3.4 c	6.1 b	6.3 b	6.8 a		44	32	28	

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other.

120-26 kg NP/ha. Fertilizer efficiency was lowest at the highest level of fertilization, increasing gradually with decreased fertilizer. Fertilizer efficiency was highest at higher plant densities. □

Effect of method of applying *Azospirillum brasilense* on rice yield

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Azospirillum brasilense Tarrand *et al.* fixes atmospheric N in soil. We studied methods of applying bacterium to increase yield. Peat-based *A. brasilense* inoculum (6 kg/ha) containing 10⁸ bacteria/g of peat soil was used for all treatments.

For seed treatment, 60 kg of seeds were soaked for 24 h in 60 liters water containing 6 kg peat-based inoculum. The seeds were allowed to sprout, then sown in the nursery. For seedling treatment, seedling roots were dipped in

Method of application of *Azospirillum* on rice yield. TNRRI, Aduthurai, India.

<i>Azospirillum</i> application method	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Seed	87	8	8.0	4.9
Seedling	86	7	1.2	4.8
Soil	86	7	1.5	4.6
Seed + seedling	88	7	8.8	5.6
Seed + soil	89	7	1.4	4.8
Seedling + soil	86	7	8.3	5.5
Seed + seedling + soil	89	8	9.3	6.5
Uninoculated (control)	84	6	6.3	4.4
CD	3	1	1.4	1.0

400 liters water containing 6 kg inoculum for 20 min and transplanted. Soil application of the bacterium was done by mixing 6 kg inoculum with 15 kg sand and broadcasting in the main field before transplanting. Inoculum also

was split into two doses and given as seed + seedling treatment or seed + soil treatment or seedling + soil treatment. In the last treatment, inoculum was split into three doses and given as seed + seedling + soil treatment.

Cultivar ADT36 was grown during Jun-Oct 1986. Plot size was 25 m² in a split-plot design replicated 3 times. Soil was clayey loam with pH 7 and CEC 36 meq/ 100 g. It had 0.13% total N,

70 kg available P/ha, and 92 kg exchangeable K/ ha. Maximum and minimum temperatures during growth were 31-39 °C and 22-28 °C. Total rainfall was 324 mm.

Split application of *A. brasilense* inoculum through seed, seedling, and soil gave the highest grain and straw yields, plant height, and number of productive tillers (see table).□

Effect of urea on decomposition of azolla

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We applied urea as a foliar spray over the azolla mat in a pot culture experiment to study azolla decomposition. One liter soil extract

medium was kept in plastic tubs and 30 g *Azolla pinnata*, *A. microphylla*, and *A. filiculoides* inoculated and maintained. Urea was added directly to the soil extract solution at 50, 100, 250, 500, 1,000, and 2,000 ppm or sprayed at 3 d after inoculation.

At 5 d after urea treatment, the decayed biomass was filtered in muslin and the moisture content removed by placing the mass on tissue paper.

With increased urea concentration,

azolla decomposition increased (see table). Urea at 2,000 ppm caused considerable weight reduction in all the 3 species of azolla. Weight reduction was highest in *A. microphylla*. Urea incorporated into the soil extract significantly activated decomposition (see figure).□

Influence of foliar spray of urea on the decomposition of azolla. Tamil Nadu, India.

Urea concentration (ppm)	Weight on 5th day after spraying					
	<i>A. pinnata</i>		<i>A. filiculoides</i>		<i>A. microphylla</i>	
	g	% decrease from initial inoculum	g	% decrease from initial inoculum	g	% decrease from initial inoculum
50	13.7	54	20.8	31	18.1	40
100	12.8	57	20.0	33	15.4	49
250	11.2	63	18.0	40	15.0	50
500	14.8	51	15.9	47	12.5	58
1000	13.3	56	13.9	54	10.5	65
2000	10.8	64	12.0	60	10.0	67
CD	0.7		0.9		1.2	

Effect of adding urea to soil extract medium on the decomposition of Azolla. Tamil Nadu, India.

Induction of callus from leaf explants of *Azolla pinnata*

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Callus from root and leaf explants of *Azolla pinnata* var. *imbricata*, Jorhat strain, was induced on two standard media: MS (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) and SH (Schenk and Hildebrandt, 1972) as such and with certain modifications in type and concentration of the hormones and cytokinins. Callus induction from leaf explants was achieved in the modified SH medium supplemented with IAA (1.0 mg/ liter),

Callus induced from *Azolla pinnata*, after 8 wk in culture, Jorhat, India.